

*Hands On — A new work from SLABS controller and generative algorithms*

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Hands On uses two arrays of pressure sensitive touch pads, one with 32 pads and another with 24. These arrays send x, y, and pressure values from all the sensors — 96 values for the 32 pad interface and 72 values for the 24 pad interface — as audio rate data. This high-rate audio-sample-synchronous transmission to the host provides for a high degree of control intimacy. A variety of mappings are used between the gesture data and the generative algorithms written in Max/MSP. Examples include massive oscillator bank synthesis, granular synthesis, physical modeling synthesis, and a variety of control structures for rhythm. In Hands On the act of composition is shifted from the sequencing of musical events towards the design of the mappings, the generative algorithms, and the overall organization of the musical material. The performance itself is the result of many hours of interactive exploration and practice with the instrument. The pressure measurements from each of the pads are mapped to dynamics allowing direct control of this important dimension for musical expression. In general, if my hands are not on the interface the instrument is silent.